

A Study on Entrepreneurship and Innovation

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Introduction

According to ‘**The father of Artificial Intelligence**’

- John McCarthy

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“Every aspect of learning or any other feature of intelligence can in principle be so precisely described that a machine can be made to stimulate it. An attempt will be made to find how to make machines use language, form abstraction and concepts, solve kinds of problems now reserved for humans, and improve themselves.”

Artificial Intelligence is a machine with the capability to perform activities and solve problems in a human manner i.e where a computer would automate a form of intelligence by learning to improve itself in solving problems and performing tasks.

Artificial Intelligence

Entrepreneurship

The ability to organise and manage business venture and to undertake risks in order to yield profits.

Innovation

‘Living in an AI world’

From Siri to Alexa to Watson, we’re living in an AI world, and the technology also affect the business and entrepreneurs. Innovation happens when you look beyond the obvious. It requires you to

identify better ways of meeting the needs of the people, some of which may not even be known to the people.

Innovation no longer remains a choice but has become an imperative. Innovation in Artificial Intelligence for an organisation is like a trump card in the game. It paves a way to a futuristic vision for the organisation and becomes a technology leader to face rapidly accelerating world.

Review of Literature

1. Name of the Authors - Kelly Fish, Paula Ruby

Published – International Journal of Entrepreneurship-13,2009

Many small businesses intend to increase their sales margin but may not have the adequate capital to begin with. Hence the entrepreneurs shy away from exploring global market. Thus artificial intelligence methodology opens up various opportunities in the global market for these small businesses to choose the right and feasible business.

2. Name of the Authors - Bo-hu-li, Bao-cun-hou, Wen Tao Yu

Published – Frontiers of Info Tech and Electronic engineering, January 2017

On the basis of the study into the application of artificial intelligence technology into manufacturing industries in the recent times, it can be analysed that with the rise in the artificial intelligence revolution there is a dynamic development of integrated technologies in the new era of ‘Internet Plus Artificial Intelligence’ which in turn has brought a substantial change in models means and the ecosystems of the manufacturing sector and in the development of artificial intelligence.

3. Name of the Authors –Prof Spyros Makridakis.

Published – International journal ,2017.03.006

The impact of the industrial and digital revolution has a vital effect on all aspects of our society, life, firms and employment. The study states about the various effects on forms and employment that would be considerable and leading in richly interconnected businesses with decision making based on the analysis of big data and greater, global competition among firms. The concern that would prove to be a challenge for the firms is using the Artificial technologies, providing several opportunities for both new products and services and thereby making productivity improvements.

4. Name of the Authors -Andrew Droll, Shanzad Khan, Ensanullan Ekhlas, StoyanTanev

Published – Technology innovation management 7(6),2017

The study states about the web research, to evaluate the growth and development of emerging technology start-ups and existing firms in the precision medicine sector. It considers the establishment of drug companies operating on medical fields and discussion focusing on their potential growth. It ultimately reveals that the existence of correlations would involve future work to include analysing the company’s growth using techniques found in web content scraping, natural language processing and machine learning.

5. Name of the Authors-Ajay Agarwal

Published –Mckinsey Quarterly, April 2018

It conveys how Artificial Intelligence would be helpful in improving existing goods and services and by enabling automation of many activities to largely increase the effectiveness with which they are produced. However, it might have an adverse effect on the economy by rendering services such as new general purpose – ‘new method of invention’ that can remould the nature of innovation process and the organisation of Research and Development.

Objectives

1. To study the impact and the positive growth of the forthcoming Artificial Intelligence revolution.
2. Automate monotonous business activities.
3. To investigate the Innovation in artificial intelligence which are creating productivity opportunities for business and the economy.

4. Reshaping of employment and the future of Artificial Intelligence.

Limitation

1. Time bound
2. Our research is purely based on entrepreneurship and innovation which does not aid any of the other sector.
3. A systematic search for the data was conducted based on the research papers published between 2009-2018.

Scope of Study

The study aims to investigate the implementation of artificial intelligence in the various fields of business ventures. Adoption of artificial intelligence is capable of automating business intelligence and providing all-inclusive end-to-end solution.

Banking and Finance-fraud detection

Various banks have accessed the help of artificial intelligence to detect fraudulent activities. The artificial intelligence software is trained to detect fraudulent and non-fraudulent transactions.

Retail-online customer support

Business reputation can be marred by its customer service, dealing with a huge volume of calls, complaints and inquires can be burdensome. With the use of chatbot, ones can easily manage their clients efficiently and appreciate prompt responses.

Security

Business security is enhanced with the help of artificial intelligence monitoring the malicious elements from getting access to the highly business sensitive database and information. Businesses in recent times, also use deep autoencoder networks and superior AI cybersecurity solutions for detecting fraud and ensure that their data is protected.

Time Management

Artificial intelligence can eliminate many monotonous and time-consuming tasks, thereby increasing the effectiveness, efficiency and productivity. It is convenient, which in turn helps the business organisation to pay more attention on imperative decisions.

Portfolio management

Artificial Intelligence have made investing effortless. It helps the stakeholders providing sound financial advices to balance the risk and to choose the right and precise investment mix and policies. It helps in smart investing and nifty tracking of the investment assets, properties, stocks and funds.

Creation of invisible User Interface

It's the next vision of the future which is an allure in the AI world. It helps in the personalization of the company's users and helps in pre-populated future interactions, it develops a new experience

and explore new technology. It also helps in

Statement of the Problem

“ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IS KILLING JOBS AND REPLACING HUMANS?” “On an estimation, 80% of the enterprise executive say AI makes workers more productive and creates jobs”

The greatest danger of Artificial intelligence is that people conclude too early that they understand it. Artificial Intelligence is poised to substitute tasks not jobs. Machine intelligence makes human morals more important. One of the significant concerns upraised against the upsurge in the use and advancement of Artificial Intelligence is if it will replace humans and whether humans will be underrated in the workplace. However, man needs to understand that instead of considering Artificial Intelligence as threat, one can learn how to use it as an opportunity to enhance their lives. Artificial Intelligence has the ability to increase the quality of the services while at the same time decreases the costs. Artificial Intelligence can also result greatly decrease our workload, reduce burnout and save hours spent on less vital tasks through automation.

As rightly said by Satya Nadella CEO: Microsoft – “Artificial Intelligence could create more jobs, not just eliminate them.”

Research Methodology

We aim to provide our understanding on the basis of the collected secondary data and present our insights and understanding about the impact of Artificial Intelligence in the field of entrepreneurship and innovation as per the recent trends and statistics.

Data Analysis

According to Digiday, the artificial intelligence market is estimated to reach \$5.1 billion worldwide by 2020. According to BCG study - India ranks third in terms of Artificial Intelligence implementation. The prime reason organisation currently seeks the help of artificial intelligence for - **48.5%- Automated communications**, which gives business speculators the information they can use to make efficient business decisions.

13.6% -Automated communications, gives customers data that can be useful to make proper decisions.

6.1%-Automation eradicates manual and reiterative tasks.

4.6%-Monitoring and alerts about the position of the business.

4.6%-Automated data- driven reporting

19.6%- All of the above

3%- Others

On the other hand, artificial intelligence as an innovation is widely used AI- powered solution with approx. 31.8% engaging voice recognition and response. According to estimates AI industry was USD 5 billion market place by revenue in 2015 and by 2020 there will be exponential improvement resulting in double revenue to USD12.5 billion i.e. it is expected to grow by 20% CAGR. “

Emerging market players show more courage when it comes to Artificial Intelligence and they keep identifying opportunities to apply the new technologies and improve them on an ongoing basis.” - said study’s author Daniel Kipper : BCG Partner and Global head of firms.

Artificial Intelligence offers expertise assistance, supplies chain network, enhances business opportunities and its rise resulting in gushing productivity which will branch a plethora of opportunities for the integration of the task forces and the man power.

Findings

- Paytm is all set to go global. According to reports its said to join hands with top investor Softbank to launch digital payment services.
- The National Health Services in the UK has employed an AI-powered chatbot which is a non-emergency helpline. The patients enter their symptoms into the app. It will, then, access a large medical database and the patients will receive personalized responses based on the information they have entered.
- General Electric is a very good example of a large multi-faceted conglomerate that has implemented AI magnificently at a large scale, across several roles, to develop from industrial and consumer products leading to 'digital industrial'. General Electricals procurement and integration of innovative AI start-ups such as "SmartSignal" has successfully show cased artificial intelligence for its rapid growth.
- Amazon's AI-powered voice assistant Alexa is surpassing the industry standards to retail-to-technology and has turned out to be a highly successful innovation in the modern era. Amazon revealed that Alexa had "far exceeded expectations" in 2017, and it contributed to the firm's 38 percent revenue growth.
- Intelligent personal assistance – they use location data, user input and a series of database information to perform requests from both voice command as well as text. Google's duplex is now improving at a greater pace, nearly exquisitely replicating human voice and conversational navigation.
- The intelligence explosion is a possibility outcome for humanity building artificial general intelligence. Artificial General Intelligence is competent of recursive self improvement leading to meteoric emergence of artificial super intelligence, the limit of which are obscure.

Conclusion

"Artificial Intelligence is in a 'golden age' and solving problems that were once in the realm of sci-fi." Entrepreneurs of today are best prepared to face the challenges of the dynamic growth of artificial intelligence which acts as an intangible asset and a means of bridging the innovation gap and heading towards the creation of a utopian future. Artificial Intelligence evolution is being piloted by exponential growth. When the obsolete patterns are broken, new worlds emerge.

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